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Cellular senescence and the exhaustion program are transcriptionally similar.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Cellular senescence was characterized by induction of genes that define the exhaustion program, including PD-L1, TIGIT, and the TOX transcription factors.